

**REVIEW: FLORICA ORȚAN - EDUCATIONAL
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Published in 2021, at Trei Publishing House, as a revised and revised edition of a work with the same title, published at Oradea University Publishing House in 2002, the volume *Educational Management* proves not only consistent (almost 500 pages, compared to less than 250 in the first edition) but also particularly useful in school and university practice and especially significant from a theoretical point of view. From the very first pages, the author reveals the context in which the study was conceived and started, the permanent dialogue between traditional pedagogy, the new sciences of education, in a wider framework of interdisciplinarity and the convergence trends between the sciences of education and economic and social management

In the first chapters, the focus is on a pertinent, sustained, interesting notional analysis, highlighting the driving substrate of training activities, the fact that "training appears as a psychosocial, double-decisional activity, where the teacher's decision actively interacts with the student's decision" (Orğan, 2021, p. 14).

The chapters reserved for the study of the principles and functions of educational management are based on the author's conviction that the managerial decision, especially in education, is based on psychosocial techniques, identification, collection, analysis of information from as many different fields as possible (both informational and psychocognitive). It is requested in this sense, the insightful distinction of "pure scientific knowledge" from "pedagogically processed knowledge" (idem, p. 46). Pedagogical creativity is also conceived as an adaptation of managerial action to the concrete conditions so varied in school and university institutions, ensuring the accessibility of knowledge, including through logical and psychological operations etc.

New, theoretically original, interdisciplinary elements regarding the styles, personalities and values of educational management are brought to the fore. They are ingeniously shown to condition school and university performance. Particularly interesting aspects appear in the chapter devoted to decision, the relations between it and information, control, guidance and evaluation. On this occasion, numerous correspondences between the formative and decision-making aspects are revealed. The information saturation specific to the educational field does not exclude decision-making in conditions of uncertainty, which also reveals the value of the human factor, the inventiveness and creativity of the decision-maker, and does not exclude individual responsibility. Commenting on the model of the correlation between individual and organizational responsibility, proposed

by Georgeta and Ion Ovidiu Pânișoara, the author notes its usefulness not only in school and university activities but also in mentoring, coaching, permanent education etc., which denotes an impressive force of generalization. The chapters on conflict management and negotiation, stress, early education, etc. can also be recommended for usefulness and resourcefulness.

The study is primarily of great interest for teachers and school managers but also for educational sciences researchers, in the context of new managerial theories and general interdisciplinary and transdisciplinary research directions.